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ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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STRUGGLING WITH INTERNATIONAL TRAFFIC DRUGS

ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the search for political instruments to counter the international drug business. The importance of the leading role of the UN, interregional organizations to combat drug trafficking, and international cooperation programs to prevent drug trafficking was noted.

Also, the article deals with the problem of the spread of drug addiction among some of the youth, as well as the fight against drug addiction, and the positions of the current issue in the country are considered. The experience of foreign countries in this area, especially the prevention and prevention of drug addiction among individuals of the population, is considered. Measures are proposed that may possibly limit this antisocial phenomenon.

Key words: UN conventions, anti-drug policy, drugs, drug trafficking, drug business, drug addiction, struggle, harm, crime, smuggling, proposals.

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ХАЛҚАРО НАРКОБИЗНЕСГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақола халқаро гиёҳвандлик воситалари савдосига қарши курашиш учун сиёсий воситаларни излашга бағишланган. Гиёҳвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний айланишига қарши курашда БМТнинг, минтақалараро ташкилотларнинг етакчи роли муҳимлиги, гиёҳвандлик воситаларнинг ноқонуний айланишининг олдини олиш бўйича халқаро ҳамкорлик дастурлари муҳимлиги қайд этилди. Шунингдек, мақолада айрим ёшлар ўртасида гиёҳвандликнинг тарқалиши муаммоси, гиёҳвандликка қарши кураш масалалари кўриб чиқилиб, мамлакатимизда долзарб мавзудаги қарашлар кўриб чиқилган. Бу борадаги хорижий мамлакатлар тажрибаси айниқса, аҳолининг алоҳида шахслари ўртасида гиёҳвандликнинг олдини олиш борасидаги ишлар кўриб чиқилган. Ушбу ғайриоддий ҳодисани чеклаш мумкин бўлган чора-тадбирлар тақлиф этилган.

Калит сўзлар: БМТ конвенциялари, гиёҳвандликка қарши сиёсат, наркотрафик, гиёҳвандлик воситалари савдоси, гиёҳвандлик, курашиш, зарар, жиноят, контрабанда, тақлифлар.

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БОРЬБА С МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫМ ОБОРОТОМ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена вопросам поиска политических инструментов противодействия международному наркобизнесу. Отмечено значение главенствующей роли ООН, межрегиональных организаций противодействия незаконному обороту наркотиков, программам международного сотрудничества по предупреждению наркобизнеса.

Также в статье рассмотрена проблема распространения наркомании среди части молодёжи, так же борьбе с наркоманией, и рассмотрены позиции актуального вопроса по стране. Рассмотрен опыт зарубежных стран в данной сфере, особенно профилактики и предупреждения наркозависимости среди отдельных лиц населения. Предложены меры, которые возможно могут ограничивать данное антисоциальное явление.

Ключевые слова: конвенции ООН, антинаркотическая политика, наркотики, наркотрафик, наркобизнес, наркомания, борьба, вред, преступление, контрабанда, предложения.

The drug problem continues to grow inexorably from year to year. International drug traffickers are becoming more aggressive and expansionist, attacking new markets with new drugs, ever-changing distribution patterns, and increasing skill in hiding and managing the money from their sales.

Even more worrying is that they are using their growing resources to interfere in the democratic and economic processes of countries through political influence and capture of key business and financial services sectors.

At the beginning of the XXI century, countries of the world have found themselves in the sphere of activity of transnational organized criminal organizations specializing in drug trafficking. The cooperation of states with this type of crime began in the 20th century. An example of this is the conclusion in November 1906 in Brussels of the International Agreement on the adoption of uniform methods for the manufacture of potent drugs [1].

Then, in the course of The Hague conferences, by 1912, principles were developed that formed the basic principles of international drug control. During and after the Second World War, there was a surge in drug use by combatants.

That is why already on December 11, 1946, the Protocol amending the agreements, conventions and protocols on drugs concluded in The Hague was signed; November 19, 1948 - Protocol extending international control to medicinal substances not subject to the Convention of July 13, 1931 on the limitation of the manufacture and control of the distribution of narcotic drugs, as amended by the Protocol signed at Lake Success on December 11 1946 On June 23, 1953, the states signed the Protocol on the Limitation and Regulation of Opium Poppy Cultivation, Production, International and Domestic Trade and Use of Opium [2].

The most important document that determined the international legal framework for combating drug trafficking was the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961. It predetermined the use of narcotic drugs exclusively for scientific and medical purposes.

In the course of the process of improving the international legal norms governing the partnership of states in this area, the Convention on Psychotropic Substances of 1971 was adopted, which established a system of international control over psychotropic substances. In 1988, the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances was adopted, which focuses on the confiscation of proceeds from the sale of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, materials and equipment for their production [3].

It defined money-laundering offenses and provided that parties to the Convention should treat them as dangerous criminal offenses and those who committed them should be severely punished and extradited. States were asked to create a mechanism for identifying and tracing such transactions, to develop procedures for the provision of banking, financial and commercial documentation that prohibits states from evading appropriate measures based on the considerations of bank secrecy.

Thus, in the XX century a full-fledged regulatory framework was formed that defines international standards for legal and illegal drug trafficking. Many states of the world, concluding bilateral agreements on cooperation between law enforcement agencies, primarily provided for cooperation in the fight against organized crime and drug trafficking.

It must be recognized that the cooperation of states in the fight against drug trafficking in the second half of the 20th century took place under the influence of the confrontation between the two military-political blocs and developed most successfully within this framework.

The combination of these factors, including the closeness of the countries of the socialist community, predetermined the relatively low level of drug addiction of their population. Drugs at the end of the 20th century created a real threat to the political, economic and social institutions of society, the gene pool of nations. Today, more than 200 million people in the world suffer from drug addiction [3].

International cooperation of states in the fight against drug trafficking since the last decades of the 20th century. It is carried out within the framework of the Conventions defining anti-drug policy with the main role of UN bodies. The main intergovernmental body that develops policy and coordinates action on drug control is the Commission on Narcotic Drugs, which unites 53 UN member states.

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One of the main activities of the UN Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, established by ECOSOC under UN General Assembly resolution 46/152 of December 18, 1991, was the coordination of the efforts of states in the field of combating drug trafficking⁶. The ongoing management of the work is carried out by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). Regularly at the sessions of the Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, much attention is paid to the work of the UNODC Center for International Crime Prevention.

Under the new conditions, the Center focuses on those regions of the world where the problem of organized transnational crime is acute, since significant changes have occurred in the structure and dynamics of organized crime at the national and transnational levels in recent years.

Along with the high level of drug trafficking, the number of crimes associated with drug trafficking has increased - money laundering, human trafficking, terrorism, migration, etc. Since organized crime has become more sophisticated and global in nature, the Commission recognized that the most important element in the fight against this phenomenon becomes international cooperation [4].

To improve activities in this area, the UNODC Center for International Crime Prevention has set up a bank on organized crime, which is accessed via the World Wide Web. The Center also prepared proposals for a project to assess the main and newly emerging criminal groups involved in transnational organized crime, according to the degree of danger they pose [5].

Great assistance is provided by UNODC in the field of training. Its experts develop training programs that include aspects of law enforcement such as crime prevention techniques, drafting of orientations, collection of information on individuals, risk assessment and screening at land borders, at sea and at airports, the use of controlled delivery, the description of existing and new chemical precursor substances, etc. The computerized training program is currently being implemented in 19 countries in 13 languages; about 50,000 officials have been trained [6].

Cooperation between states in the fight against drug trafficking is actively developing within the framework of Interpol. As you know, the second - the police department of the Organization, along with other types of crime, is also involved in investigating crimes related to drug trafficking.

The structure of the INTERPOL bodies involved in drug trafficking includes the Bangkok Bureau, based in Thailand, a large Asian region of global drug trafficking. Interpol's National Central Bureaus have departments to combat drug trafficking.

In 1975, close cooperation was initiated in the fight against crime by 12 Western European states: Belgium, Great Britain, Greece, Denmark, Ireland, Spain, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Portugal, Germany and France. It was decided to create a group "TREVII" [7] and to hold regular meetings of the Ministers of the Interior (Justice), heads of police and security agencies to coordinate the fight against crime.

One of the priority areas of activity was the fight against drug trafficking. Cooperation in this area became closer after the creation of Europol in 1995, although the full-fledged organization began to work later. The period after November 1998, when a multilateral conference at the level of ministers of the interior "International police cooperation in the fight against organized crime and corruption" was held in Strasbourg, was a landmark in the activities of Europol against drugs.

Delegations from 33 European states, as well as representatives of the UN, Interpol, the European Union and Europol took part in its work. The conference confirmed the readiness of all member states of the Council of Europe to strengthen cooperation in the fight against crime, including drug and arms trafficking, money laundering and corruption [8].

The annual volume of illicit drug sales on the streets is currently estimated at more than US\$500 billion per year. This amount is more than the national budgets of many countries. Increasingly, we see drug traffickers collaborating with terrorist groups, using drugs to buy weapons. Thus, the drug trade affects the political, social and economic stability of nation states.

The main victims of drugs are and will be those young people who are trapped and addicted to drugs. However, while street crime may still become increasingly apparent as a threat to our daily security, it is the steady rise in power of large-scale criminal organizations that fuel the growth of drug trafficking that is the main threat of our time.

The international drug trade is highly organized. Traffickers can use the best minds, be it legal, financial, logistical. They use state-of-the-art equipment and technology to manufacture, transport and distribute their medicines and to help launder money from them.

The biggest drug traffickers can now manage and finance all of their activities without coming into contact with the drugs themselves, and in many cases living, thanks to satellite communications, on yachts or in countries where the law can't actually touch them.

They remain unscathed because they can rarely be linked to specific drug smuggling operations or where they are located, no evidence of their guilt can be established. With their boundless wealth, drug lords can buy protection from prosecution.

The flow of heroin from Asia, cocaine from South America, cannabis from North Africa and synthetic drugs from European bases is unstoppable. Larger and more frequent customs seizures may indicate greater success in tracing drug shipments.

Most often, these seizures are a sign of increased drug flow. The real success of drug seizures in a country can only be truly measured if elements of street price and cleanliness are added to the equation. If prices are low and purity is high, large seizures will only confirm greater drug availability.

In terms of law and order, we see that in some developed countries, police forces and customs are cooperating much more effectively in the war on drugs than they did ten or even five years ago. But they are still under-equipped and understaffed.

While we are congratulating ourselves on being able to do without customs officers as our borders converge, we are throwing away a trained resource that will increasingly be seen as essential to prosecuting major drug criminals. If we cannot match the human traffickers in providing the best technical, electronic and chemical analysis equipment available, we will fight with one hand tied behind our backs.

The Commission's report to the Council and the European Parliament on the European Union Action Plan on Drugs for the period 1995-1999 is a factual, restrained, but rather boring document. Of course, it has positive elements.

Among them, it is emphasized that effective action against drugs requires a comprehensive and integrated approach, but does not sufficiently identify those issues that require the highest priority, or convincingly call for better use or increased allocation of funds.

The Commission remains polite in the face of the waste of crop replacement funds and does not make clear distinctions between the circle leaders among drug dealers, wholesalers, retailers and small time traders. This is not an argument in favor of at least an equal distribution of funds for prevention and rehabilitation.

He cannot, even on the basis of speculation, point to a lack of unity on drug matters in his own departments and between the Council and the Commission, which have different powers under the Treaty on European Union.

He completely fails to acknowledge that our drug policy to date has failed to cope with the growing power of drug traffickers and curb the ever-increasing influence of black money in our society. In short, there is no sense of urgency. Therefore, it is important that this Parliament and its Committee on Civil Liberties help to identify where the main problems lie and put forward additional and consistent recommendations to improve the situation [9].

The European Commission report addresses three areas:

- Actions to reduce demand;
- Actions to combat drug trafficking;
- Actions in the international sphere.

Let's look at the fight against drugs in France:

The law of 31 December 1970 constitutes the current legal basis for France's drug policy. Its aims are: strict suppression of human trafficking; prohibit drug use, but also offer alternatives to stopping drug use; to provide free and anonymous care for users who seek treatment.

This law clearly distinguishes between two aspects: the suppression of drug use and drug trafficking. With regard to illegal drug use, the 1970 law has sparked lively discussions between pro-prohibition and pro-prohibition advocates since its passage. At the request of governments, three successive reports were prepared (Pelletier 1978, Trautman 1990, Henrion 1995) on the approach to drug policy and, in particular, on the 1970 law [10].

Although this law has not been amended since then, ministerial directives have been issued to harmonize the practice of law enforcement and health services. In particular, the Directive of 17 June 1999 concerning judicial action against drug addicts recommends that prosecutors *inter alia* base their actions against offenders who use drugs on health-related principles. Indeed, this orientation constitutes one of the main points of the 1999 French plan of action against drugs.

Drug control in the USA.

In 1986, Congress passed the Drug Abuse Enforcement Act, which established mandatory minimum prison terms for certain drug offenses.

This law was later heavily criticized as having racist ramifications, as it provided for longer prison sentences for offenses involving the same amount of crack cocaine (which is more commonly used by black Americans) than powdered cocaine (which is more commonly used by white Americans).

Five grams of crack automatically led to a five-year sentence, while it took 500 grams of powdered cocaine to merit the same sentence.

Critics also pointed to data showing that people of color were targeted and arrested on suspicion of drug use more frequently than whites. Overall, this policy has led to a rapid increase in the number of people imprisoned for non-violent drug-related crimes.

In 2014, almost half of the 186,000 people serving time in federal prisons in the United States were jailed for drug-related charges, according to the Federal Bureau of Prisons.

Public support for the war on drugs has waned in recent decades. Some Americans and politicians believe the campaign was ineffective or led to a racial divide. Between 2009 and 2019, about 40 states took steps to relax their drug laws, reduce fines and reduce mandatory minimum sentences, according to the Pew Research Center.

In 2010, Congress passed the Fair Sentencing Act (FSA), which reduced the discrepancy between crack and powdered cocaine offenses from 100:1 to 18:1. The recent legalization of marijuana in several states and the District of Columbia has also led to a more tolerant political outlook on recreational drug use. Technically, the war on drugs is still going on, but with less intensity and less publicity than in its early years.

People who don't realize or simply don't care about the danger end up trapped in drugs at the end of the day due to feelings of curiosity and feeling like they're in the spotlight. In the end, unfortunately, this process ends in death. The global drug problem is attracting more and more attention. According to the World Drug Report 2021-2022, 29.5 million people suffer from drug use disorders and drug dealers are constantly improving their products.

Drug addicts often find themselves in social isolation, which makes it difficult for them to recover and reintegrate into society. The United Nations continues to support human rights-based drug control and capacity-building strategies in areas such as health, criminal justice and prison management, as well as in civil society organizations, to ensure that drug addicts and prisoners have better access to existing services, including HIV services.

In the area of alternative development to displace drug crops, the United Nations is supporting rural populations by providing legitimate income-generating opportunities, primarily through the establishment of sustainable markets for cash crops [11].

In conclusion, I would like to note that preventive measures include public videos, information sessions, educational programs for parents and young people about substance abuse. Thanks to these preventive works, people, having received enough information about the deadly effects of drugs, try to protect themselves from this deadly problem. It helps people and society become healthier both mentally and physically.

In this regard, I would like to give some suggestions for the prevention and control of narcotic substances:

1. Take up the fight against drugs, considering it as a matter of the destiny of the nation.
2. Include the fight against drugs as the main political direction of the state in the program of socio-economic development;
3. Pursue a comprehensive drug control strategy.
4. Consider the fight against drugs as a complex social system program and a long-term strategic task in which it is necessary to apply legal, administrative, economic, cultural, educational and medical means in order to mobilize and organize all the forces of society in the fight against drugs.
5. Fight drugs on a legal basis. Guided by the strategy of governing the country on a legitimate basis, continuously develop and improve the legal and legislative system for combating drugs;
6. Expand the work on the treatment and restoration of health and saving the lives of drug addicts - all so that the fight against drugs goes within the framework of the legal order.
7. Simultaneously focus on the four main areas of the fight against drugs:
 - prohibit the use, trade, sowing and production of drugs;
 - to cut off the sources of narcotic drugs, strictly according to the law to take measures both against the drug business and against the consumption of drugs.
8. Block the sources and cut off the supply and distribution of drugs, establish control over both the illegal supply and abuse of narcotic drugs, and stop any kind of drug-related crimes.

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